

Development of web scraping tool to extract multilingual data

*1st simran N. Maniyar
departement of computer science
and Teachnology, Dr.Babasaheb
Ambedkar Marathwada University
Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, India

2nd Dr.Sonali B. Kulkarni
departement of computer science
and Teachnology, Dr.Babasaheb
Ambedkar Marathwada University
Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, India

3rd Gaju S. Chavan departement of
computer science and Teachnology,
Dr.Babasaheb Ambedkar
Marathwada University Chhatrapati
Sambhajnagar, India

Received: Jun 25, 2025

Accepted: July 16, 2025

Published: July 25, 2025

Abstract

Web scrapping is process of extracting data from the internet through a variety of ways or procedures. It was designed for extracting data on social media. While researching several online scraping technologies available for gathering reviews, but they have some limitations and most of web scrapper system working only English data but some people want Marathi, Hindi review for their project. It is quite difficult to extract manually. This is big challenging for us. That's why we decided to create our own web scraper tool specifically for Extracting Multilingual social media data. In this paper we focus on develop a Multilingual Web Scraper tool. It was develop to make the process of gathering reviews from various websites more efficient. Extracting reviews has become a much easier operation as technology has advanced, allowing us to collect a large amount of data. This tool scrapping data in Hindi, Marathi and English, As a result, data scraping had an 80% success rate.

Keywords: Social media, Languages, web scrapping, websites, Natural language Processing

I. Introduction:

Web scraping is an important technology for speeding data collecting, especially in big data applications and Natural language processing applications. In natural language processing Machine translation, sentiment analysis, text summarization, etc. Machine translations means we translate source language to target language [1]. Sentiment Analysis is process of inspecting pieces of text as positive, neutral, negative [2]. Summarization is defined as the extraction of features of text document and generating abstract with same meaning.[3]. All domains require data, and gathering it can be a considerable burden. Data is required for analysis, decision-making, and gaining insights in a variety of industries, including business, healthcare, and

research. However, gathering this information is not always simple. Social media networks are currently one of the most significant sources of data. These platforms host massive amounts of user-generated content, which can be quite useful in analysing trends, sentiments, and behaviours. However, manually pulling data from social media is a difficult and time-consuming process. The sheer volume of data, combined with the dynamic nature of social media, renders manual collecting unfeasible.

This is when web scraping comes into play. Web scraping has evolved as an important tool for collecting this information efficiently. Web scraping, also known as web extraction or harvesting, is the process of extracting data from the World Wide Web (WWW) and saving it to a file system or database for later retrieval or analysis. This method can be performed manually by a user or automatically by a bot or web crawler, which typically uses the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) or a web browser. Given the huge and ever-changing environment of data on the WWW, web scraping has emerged as an effective way for obtaining large data. Modern online scraping techniques have progressed from simple, ad hoc operations to complex, customised systems capable of managing a wide range of scenarios. Today's advanced web scraping systems not only scan markup languages or JSON files, but also incorporate computer visual analytics and natural language processing, allowing them to simulate human browsing behaviour while engaging with web information [4].

Web scraping is an important for automating data collection operations. This work attempts to fill this need by creating a versatile web scraper capable of capturing data from any website and doing subsequent analysis.[5] The scraper's success is shown by its use on many websites, including Amazon, Flipkart, and Jagran Josh, where reviews can be extracted. To demonstrate its capabilities, the results are incorporated into an interface that includes data visualisation tools for extensive analysis. One of the most notable aspects of this web scraper is its capacity to extract reviews or data in many languages, including Hindi, Marathi, and English, giving it the title of Multilingual Web Scraper. It can return results in 50 seconds, which is optimised to support websites that require longer processing periods. While originally built for a 10-second processing window, changes were made to ensure compatibility with other websites. Our tool distinguishes itself from other scrapers by focusing on language.

With the growing interest in linguistic research and social media evaluations, our web scraper is a useful resource for scholars and professionals working in this field our web scraper works by first entering the target website URL and then determining the specific class or tag where the requested data is placed. By focusing on these characteristics, the scraper extracts just the most relevant information, resulting in a clean and efficient output. This web scrapper save scrapped data in CSV files also. The web scraper grabbed five sites, analysed the data, and visualised it all in about 50 seconds. However, limits were discovered, particularly in terms of applicability to specific product names and the extraction of needed information from the generated items. Additionally, BeautifulSoup's speed optimisation resulted in the inability to extract all available data. We develop this web scrapper for Multiple domains like sentiment analysis, text summarization, machine translation [6] etc. apart of them we working on sentiment analysis domain and we search different types of web scrapping tools for extracting review but some reason it's not working for me I need huge data it's not possible take a manually that's why we thought why not develop our own web scrapper. We design our own Multilingual Web scrapper. Now this is very easy for me extract review on different websites.

II. Related Work:

As Internet technology evolves, the concept of big data gains prominence, owing to the expansion of artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, cloud computing, and our daily online activities. This glut of data has become indispensable in a variety of industries, including e-commerce, O2O services, and logistics, propelling their growth. Big data enables firms to forecast consumer behaviour by analyzing large databases, allowing for more informed decision-making. While the significance of data may not be obvious to the general public, scholars use it to foresee market trends with great success. As a result, technologies such as data scraping have emerged as critical study topics, emphasizing the significance of successfully utilizing and interpreting data.

Ayat Abodayeh et.al: They studied despite several web scraping solutions, Python's BeautifulSoup module is very underutilised. As a result, the goal of this research is to create a web scraper that can harvest data from a variety of websites and then do analyses. The web scraper was used on the Amazon platform to capture important product information such as name, price, review count, rating, and relevant links. To demonstrate its effectiveness, the

scraper's output was included into an interface that combined data visualisation techniques for complete analysis. Limitations were discovered, particularly in customising the scraper for

specific product names and extracting needed information from the collected dataset. Furthermore, due to efficiency constraints, BeautifulSoup may not extract all available data [7][5]. **David Mathew Thomas et.al**: work on Conventional techniques of information analysis rely on root-impact relationships, which include qualitative and quantitative studies as well as extrapolation analyses. This study compares the ethical and procedural aspects of web scraping, explaining its design and functionality. The procedure consists of three major steps: pulling desirable links from the web, getting data from these links, and storing the data in a CSV file. Python is the preferred implementation language due to its strong community support and elegant writing style, making it perfect for scraping data from multiple websites in an efficient and ethical manner.[8]

Lusiana Citra Dewi et.al: Research on The wealth of information available on the internet, particularly on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, frequently overwhelms users with unnecessary or redundant items shown in timelines or feeds. This study presents a Web Scraping method to solve this problem by effectively searching, aggregating, and presenting information based on user preferences. The system designed for this purpose makes use of APIs provided by Facebook and Twitter Developers, as well as regular expressions (Regex) for text matching patterns. The study's trials show that the proposed strategy effectively eliminates information overload, minimises redundancy, and modifies information relevance to better suit user preferences by arranging data in a database.[9][20]

Kasereka Henrys et.al : Scraping data from the internet uses a variety of strategies, as highlighted by Wikipedia in 2021. These include both basic methods like manual copy and paste and more modern approaches like text grabbing and regular expressions. Additionally, programming techniques like as Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) programming, Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML) parsing, and Document Object Model (DOM) parsing are widely used. Other approaches include the use of specialized web scraping software, vertical aggregation platforms, semantic annotation recognition, and computer vision-based web page analyzers. These numerous methodologies cater to different data scraping requirements and tastes, providing a variety of possibilities for obtaining information from web sources.[10].

A Rahmatulloh*1, R Gunawan et.al : This study has effectively gathered scientific article data from Google Scholar. Through experiments, the implementation of web scraping using the HTML DOM method on Google Scholar yielded promising results. Specifically, it retrieved 238 researcher data from Web Scholar, comprising 9 attributes and a total of 2,523 articles. The acquired data can be manipulated for visual representation or converted into formats such as .xlsx or .pdf for further analysis and presentation. [11].

Prof. P.S.Gaikwad et.al: In the world of web scraping, many tools perform distinct functions. BeautifulSoup, for example, specialises in extracting data from HTML and XML files, including features for navigating, searching, and modifying the parse tree when combined with a parser. In contrast, Selenium excels in scraping enormous amounts of data, including text and images, in a short period of time. It orchestrates web browsers such as Chrome, Firefox, and Opera via the WebDriver protocol, which is generally used for cross-browser compatibility and end-to-end testing. Finally, the Mysql-connector enables Python programmers to establish connections with MySQL databases, allowing for smooth data retrieval and manipulation [12]

Himawan, et.al. :Recent study has developed an automated web-based program for obtaining Instagram account data, addressing this problem by using a web scraping method. Because it avoids using Instagram's Application Programming Interface (API), which places limitations on data extraction, this solution was selected. In order to test the app, 15 Instagram accounts with publication counts ranging from 100 to 11,000 were used in the study. The outcomes showed that up to 2,412 data points per account may be successfully downloaded by the application. Users can also manage the downloaded data with this application, which lets them remove entries that aren't needed and export the data in CSV, Excel, or JSON forms, among other formats [13].

III.Approaches for web scrapping:

It is essential to comprehend the fundamental principles of web scraping in order to investigate the many strategies covered in this paper. The basics entail manipulating several parameters to appear authentic when sending a request to an endpoint. Even while a lot of websites can handle a simple HTTP request, many also include a way to tell the difference between requests from

real users and requests from bots. This study looks at a range of online scraping methods, ranked from least to most efficient at extracting data.

- **Basic Requests Library Tests:** This is the method that is most frequently used to extract data from websites. A straightforward HTTP request is made to a number of websites using the Python `requests` package, and the page contents and response status codes are then recorded
- **Timed tests using selenium:** The scraper script only ever accessed each website once in each of the earlier tests. To gather data, real-world scripts frequently run for hours or even days. Each website from a variety of categories was requested a predetermined number of times using the Selenium library in order to mimic this behaviour. Up until the point at which the website ceased answering requests, the time and number of requests were noted.
- **Requests library with header:** The `requests` package automatically includes a default user-agent header in the format `python-requests/package-version` if no user-agent is specified. This test is similar to the previous one, but it adds a user-agent header parameter to the request. Most websites use this header to identify the requesting party.

IV. Methodology for Multi-Lingual Web Scrapping

- **Multilanguage:** The Lang option specifies the desired language for the Accept-Language header in the HTTP request. The response. Encoding property is explicitly set to 'utf-8', indicating that Marathi text should be encoded as UTF-8. You may need to change this encoding depending on the encoding used by the website. The rest of the method is the same as previously, including the error handling logic. When calling the scrape_ reviews method, you can define your Marathi language preference by passing 'mr' or 'marathi' as the Lang argument.
- **Parsing HTML,:** however the underlying methods include parsing trees and traversing nodes, which are conceptually similar to graph theory and tree traversal algorithms.
 - **Tokenization** is the process of breaking down HTML code into tokens such as elements, attributes, text content, and comments.
 - **Lexing** is the process of categorising tokens and assigning them semantic significance, such as identifying opening tags, closing tags, and attributes.

- **Parsing:** Using the tokens' semantic meaning, the parser creates a tree-like data structure known as the Document Object Model (DOM). Each HTML element is transformed into a node in the DOM tree, with parent-child connections serving as relationships.
- **Traversal:** The DOM tree can be used to access and manipulate elements. Traversal entails travelling through the tree, visiting nodes, and checking their properties and contents.
- **Data Extraction:** Specific items or attributes can be extracted depending on criteria such as tag names, classes, and IDs. Extracted data can then be used for a variety of reasons, including scraping text content, extracting links, and collecting information.
- **Data Filtering and Selection:** When scraping data, you can utilise mathematical principles like set theory to filter and choose specific components based on their properties or relationships to other elements. Data selection entails identifying certain HTML elements or attributes that hold the desired data. Scraping product information can involve pulling data from components with a specified class linked with product details.
- **Error Handling:** Probability and statistics principles can be beneficial when dealing with errors, such as assessing the chances of encountering specific errors or examining the distribution of error kinds. Mathematical optimisation techniques, such as linear programming or gradient descent, may be used to optimise algorithms for efficiency and performance.
- **Identifying Potential mistakes:** Before beginning the web scraping process, it is critical to detect any potential mistakes that may arise. Common online scraping issues include connection timeouts, HTTP failures (e.g., 404 Not Found), missing elements on the webpage, and unanticipated changes in the webpage's structure.
- **Implementing Robust Error Handling:** Robust error handling entails creating ways to properly handle mistakes that may occur during web scraping. This involves leveraging Python's try-except blocks to capture and handle exceptions like timeouts, connection problems, and parsing errors.
- **Logging and reporting:** Logging is required to track errors and debug web scraping systems. Developers can accurately identify and debug problems by logging essential information such as error messages, timestamps, and the context in which the incident occurred. Furthermore, reporting systems can be used to warn developers or users of errors and provide instructions on how to correct them.

- **Retry Mechanisms:** Web scraping faults can be transient or intermittent, such as network timeouts or brief server troubles. Implementing retry methods enables the programme to automatically retry failed requests a predetermined number of times before giving up, improving the likelihood of successful data retrieval.
- **Graceful Degradation:** When mistakes occur, it is critical that the programme gradually decreases its functionality instead of crashing or exhibiting unexpected behaviour. This could include giving default values, fallback alternatives, or alternative workflows for handling incomplete or missing data.
- **User Feedback:** Providing users with relevant feedback on issues they encounter is critical for improving the user experience. This may involve showing informative error messages, recommending potential solutions or troubleshooting actions, and advising users on how to proceed in the event of a mistake.
- **GUI Layout:** When designing the GUI, you may use geometry and linear algebra techniques to place items, compute dimensions, and perform transformations.
- **Input Validation:** When validating user input, you can use discrete mathematics ideas to set limitations, such as range checks for numeric inputs and pattern matching for text inputs. Overall, while web scraping and GUI creation primarily require programming skills and domain expertise, certain mathematical principles can supplement the development process, particularly in algorithm design, data processing, and optimisation.
- **Accuracy Calculation:** The ratio of successful scrapes to all websites is multiplied by 100 to determine accuracy. It shows the proportion of websites that data was successfully scraped from.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Successful scrapes}}{\text{Total Websites}} \times 100$$

Figure 1. : Methodology of Multilingual Web scraping System

V. Implementation:

This research paper describes the creation of a web scraper for extracting social media evaluations. The procedure starts with user involvement, in which users enter the URL of the website from which they want to collect data. They next navigate to the website's HTML code and locate the element and class matching to the sort of text they wish to scrape. After entering the tag and class, the web scraper makes a request to the website. If permission is allowed to scrape the data, the web scraper retrieves the reviews; otherwise, an error indicating that the URL and class did not match is displayed. The web scraper then extracts the HTML code for the given class and tag. Following that, several functions are used to clean up the text, leaving only sanitised reviews. The cleaned reviews are then shown on the GUI, allowing users to review and assess their accuracy. If a review is judged valid, it can be saved as a CSV file. After saving the file, a confirmation message is presented.

Figure 2: System Architecture

VI. Result Discussion:

One of the most notable aspects of this web scraper is its capacity to extract reviews or data in many languages, including Hindi, Marathi, and English, giving it the title of Multilingual Web Scraper. It can return results in 50 seconds, which is optimised to support websites that require longer processing periods. While originally built for a 10-second processing window, changes were made to ensure compatibility with other websites. Our tool distinguishes itself from other scrapers by focusing on language.

Table 1: Result of scrapping data in various website

Website URL	Status	Category	Language
shiksha.com	Not extracted	Educational reviews	English
imdb.com	Worked	Movie reviews	English
gizbot.com	Not extracted	Mobile reviews	English
flipkart.com	Worked	Product reviews	English
patrika.com	Worked	News	Hindi
navbharattimes.indiatimes.com	Worked	News	Hindi
hindi.starlive24.in	Worked	News	Hindi
amarujala.com	Worked	News	Hindi
techjankari.blogspot.com	Worked	Mobile, information	Hindi
marathi.indiatimes.com	Worked	News	Marathi
marathijagran.com	Worked	News	Marathi
saamana.com	Worked	News	Marathi
lokmat.com - Rakhi Pournima	Worked	Shopping	Marathi
lokmat.com - Cricket	Worked	Cricket	Marathi

The table essentially gives an overview of the web scraping process used on various websites. It demonstrates the variety of languages and sources from which reviews were derived, with a concentration on Hindi, English, and Marathi languages. This type of data is useful for analysis in a variety of fields, including sentiment analysis, cultural insights, and market research, where understanding the distribution of reviews across languages and sources can reveal valuable insights into user preferences, interests, or trends related to specific topics or locations. Due to our system's request limit, each website initially submitted up to 100 reviews only 50 seconds. To collect more information, we ran the algorithm several times, each time retrieving an additional 100 reviews.

The dataset offers a thorough summary of numerous websites arranged according to their language, content type, and extraction status. A variety of news, product, mobile, educational, and film-related websites are included in the list. IMDb and Flipkart, two English-language websites that specialised in movie and product reviews, respectively, were successfully extracted, but Shiksha and Gizbot were not. On the other hand, news content from Hindi-language websites including Patrika, Navbharat Times, Star Live 24, and Amar Ujala was successfully extracted, and Tech Jankari also offered mobile information. Marathi-language websites with successful data extraction include Marathi.indiatimes.com, Marathijagran.com, Saamana.com, and Lokmat. These websites display a variety of topics, including news, shopping, and cricket. This combination of content kinds and languages demonstrates a wide range of data sources, reflecting the various demands and interests of consumers across linguistic regions. The success of the extraction process for the majority of the sources is demonstrated by the success of the procedure throughout various websites, and it also reveals areas where the extraction efforts were less successful. The necessity of focused methods for data extraction and classification to satisfy particular informational needs across various languages and content kinds is generally highlighted by this dataset.

VII. Conclusion

The growing interest in linguistic research and social media evaluations, our web scraper is a useful resource for scholars and professionals working in this field. This web scraper works by first entering the target website URL and then determining the specific class or tag where the requested data is placed. By focusing on these characteristics, the scraper extracts just the most relevant information, resulting in a clean and efficient output. This web scrapper save scrapped data in CSV files. The web scraper grabbed different types of websites, analysed the data, and visualised it all in about 50 seconds. We collected data for testing purposes by scraping 15 distinct websites. Data scraping was accomplished on 12 of 15 websites, yielding an accuracy of 80%.

References

- [1] Simran N. Maniyar¹ , Sonali B. Kulkarni², Pratibha R. Bhise³,” Linguistic Divergence in various Language pair in Machine Translation Perceptive”, IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering, Volume 23, Issue 1, Ser. I (Jan. – Feb. 2021)
- [2] Mariya A. Ali¹ , Dr. Sonali B. Kulkarni² .,” Preprocessing of Text for Emotion Detection and Sentiment Analysis of Hindi Movie Reviews”, International Conference on IoT based Control Networks and Intelligent Systems,2020.
- [3] Apurva D. Dhawale, Sonali B. Kulkarni, Vaishali M. Kumbhakarna,” Automatic Pre-Processing of Marathi Text for Summarization”, International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology, ISSN: 2249-8958 (Online), Volume-10 Issue-1, October 2020
- [4] Bo Zhao,” Web Scraping” , Springer International Publishing AG, 2017
- [5] A. Abodayeh, R. Hejazi, W. Najjar, L. Shihadeh and R. Latif, "Web Scraping for Data Analytics: A BeautifulSoup Implementation," 2023 Sixth International Conference of Women in Data Science at Prince Sultan University (WiDS PSU), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, 2023
- [6] S. B. Kulkarni, P. D. Deshmukh,” Linguistic Divergence Patterns in English to Marathi Translation”, International Journal of Computer Applications, Volume 87 – No.4, February 2014
- [7] Vidhi Singrodia, Anirban Mitra, Subrata Paul, “A Review on Web Scraping and its Applications”, 2019 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (IEEE), 2019, Coimbatore, INDIA
- [8] D. M. Thomas and S. Mathur, "Data Analysis by Web Scraping using Python," 2019 3rd International conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA), Coimbatore, India, 2019
- [9] Lusiana Citra Dewi, Meiliana, Alvin Chandra,”Social Media Web Scraping using Social Media Developers API and Regex”, Procedia Computer Science,Volume 157,2019, Pages 444-449, ISSN 1877-0509.
- [10] Kasereka, Henrys, “Importance of web scraping in e-commerce and e-marketing”, SSRN Electronic Journal, 2020

- [11] A. S. Bale, N. Ghorpade, R. S, S. Kamalesh, R. R and R. B. S, "Web Scraping Approaches and their Performance on Modern Websites," 2022 3rd International Conference on Electronics and Sustainable Communication Systems (ICESC), Coimbatore, India, 2022.
- [12] Prof. P.S.Gaikwad, Kaushal Parmar, Rohit Yadav, Datta Supekar,"Implementation Of Web Scraping For E-Commerce Website", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research, ISSN: 2349-5162, Vol. 8, Issue 6, page no. e882-e885, June-2021
- [13] Himawan, A., Priadana, A., & Murdiyanto, A. W. (2020). Implementation of Web Scraping to Build a Web-Based Instagram Account Data Downloader Application. *International Journal on Informatics for Development*, 9(2), 59-65. e-ISSN: 2549-7448. Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, Universitas Jenderal Achmad Yani Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, Indonesia.
- [14] Osmar Castrillo-Fernández," Web Scraping: Applications and Tools", , December 2015
- [15] S. Lunn, J. Zhu and M. Ross, "Utilizing Web Scraping and Natural Language Processing to Better Inform Pedagogical Practice," 2020 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE), Uppsala, Sweden, 2020.
- [16] Rahmatulloh, Alam & Gunawan, Rohmat, "Web Scraping with HTML DOM Method for Data Collection of Scientific Articles from Google Scholar", Indonesian Journal of Information Systems, 2020
- [17] M. Revati¹ , Ch. Raja Jacob¹ , K. Ashok¹," Data Analysis by Web Scrapping: An Application Python", Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education, Vol.13 No.03 (2022).
- [18] Priya Matta¹ , Nikita Sharma² , Devyani Sharma³ , Bhasker Pant⁴," Web Scraping: Applications and Scraping Tools", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering, ISSN 2278-3091, volume 9,2020
- [19] Navroz Kaur Kahlon¹ , Williamjeet Singh²," Comparative Analysis of Web Scraping Tools for Low-Resource Language Text", International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology, ISSN: 2231–5381, Volume 72 Issue 1, 284-299, January 2024

- [20] Grimmer, Justin. 2013. *Representational Style in Congress: What Legislators Say and Why It Matters*. Cambridge University Press.
- [21] Arbelaitz O, Gurrutxaga I, Lojo A, Muguerza J, Pérez JM, Perona I. Web usage and content mining to extract knowledge for modelling the users of the Bidasoa Turismo website and to adapt it. *Expert Systems with applications*. 2013 Dec 15;40(18):7478-91.